

Better Privacy by Server Pushing Instead of Client Pulling

Cris Pedregal-Martin

Subhasish Mazumdar

Computer Science
University of New Mexico
cris@cs.unm.edu

Computer Science
New Mexico Tech
mazumdar@cs.nmt.edu

1 Location-Awareness and Privacy

While *location awareness* offers the promise of providing valuable services to mobile clients, it is generally assumed that this process entails the user identifying herself and her location and usually publishing some profile information about her preferences vis-a-vis possible offers. For example, in order to take advantage of location-aware offers, the user must *announce* her presence to the local vendors, who know her identity and location and are thus able to track her movement and consumption patterns [5]. Another example of the tension between location-awareness and privacy is that withholding one's position while allowing colleagues to get in touch are generally incompatible [3].

These basic limitations to the privacy of the clients arise because current approaches assume that clients have to say who they are and where they are in order to participate. In this paper we reexamine these assumptions by proposing an approach that reduces client transmissions, i.e., we explore what is possible if clients try to be "silent" (i.e., not advertise their identity and location) as much as possible. We identify an interesting subset of location-aware services whose nature does not require clients to identify themselves or their location; these range from listen-only to pseudonymous to fully-disclosed interactions. Naturally, to the extent that services or goods have to be delivered, clients must reveal something about themselves. Overall, our approach enables clients to keep privacy choices under their control.

We consider a situation in which clients refrain from revealing their location, and each provider is aware of the specific location in which it is serving its offers. We say that clients practice *lazy identification*, i.e., remaining mostly *silent*, and identifying themselves and/or their location only when strictly necessary. We say that providers (or servers)

localcast information, service and goods offers, i.e., transmit *keyed by location*. This means that the provider must know its geographic and other relevant coordinates. (It is both desirable and feasible for such transmission to be limited to the vicinity of the the offered goods or services.) The matching of location and services is then done by the clients themselves.

Our approach burdens servers (by for example expecting them to arrange for broadcast disks on a per-location basis) to make it easier for clients to transmit less. This is a reflection of the inherent asymmetry of resources available to providers and clients. Providers have in comparison to clients infinite resources: computing capacity, storage, bandwidth, energy.¹ In Section 3 we flesh out a scenario of an airport which shows the range of services that can be offered and how silent clients can take advantage of them.

Often clients need to avail themselves of several different services together in order to set up an activity. We propose supporting *composition* of services while preserving privacy as much as possible. For example, a person may want to assemble an office around her portable computer, obtaining access to network, printing, communication, etc. at the airport. This service composition should not be apparent to the different providers; at least, no more apparent than the end-user application requires.

The combination of lazy-identification, *localcast*, and *composition* enables a tradeoff between location awareness and privacy. In the sequel we elaborate on these ideas with examples both of applications and the supporting technology.

2 Ingredients of Our Approach

We outline the infrastructure requirements of the approach outlined above. Although this is a preliminary treatment, in this section we show that the required ingredients are well-established concepts and technologies. Briefly, to invert the client request-server delivery of information and service offers, we propose the use of *broadcast disks*, introduced in mobile systems. To describe the services and make them composable, we propose the use of XML. To protect transactions and privacy, a large body of cryptography supports secure, anonymous, and pseudonymous communications and transactions. We elaborate on each of these below.

In the sequel we consider persons (the *principals*) and their mobile computers interacting with *services* and *service providers* (or *servers*). We sometimes conflate a principal with its client or express a principal's needs as those of its client. We sometimes also conflate an organization offering a service with its realization in software, hardware and communication infrastructure, and the service itself.

¹While our approach in principle burdens clients with storing and manipulating data, we expect that their reduced needs for transmission will yield savings of energy, likely to be the most limiting of clients' resources.

Broadcast Disks were proposed as an information system architecture that exploits the asymmetry in bandwidth between the server and a client by requiring the server to continuously and repeatedly broadcast data to the clients [1]. The provider² enables clients to answer their queries by anticipating them in the data it transmits. This scheme is likened to a disk, in that clients await their desired data to come around in a cyclical transmission. Optimization is effected by repeating different data items at different frequencies using the metaphor of the superimposition of a number of disks. For our purposes, how to arrange the data broadcast to best serve a diversity of clients is a solved problem.

We envision servers that offer goods or services to clients as an interesting problem domain in which to consider the tension between location-awareness and privacy. These may be offered via broadcast disk, and motivate the need for open and standard means of describing and composing them.

For a given offer, the localcast contains a description of the service or product offered, a price, availability, and delivery information. For example, in the case of a physical item (e.g., a cup of coffee), this may include coordinates or directions to an outlet; in the case of a service (e.g., a movie on demand), it may include connectivity and protocol requirements and network addresses. Such components must be self-describing using a language such as XML and various categories of service would use a schema that introduces the semantics for its domain. This service orientation is consistent with the current focus of business process management [8, 4].

The client needs to have the ability to interpret the stream of services available at a location and filter it using its current needs. This is feasible given recent work, for example on filtering XML streams through pre-defined predicate(s) [2]. Clients should also have the ability to compose several services to achieve an overall objective [7, 6], without unduly sacrificing privacy. Work related to composability ranges from network protocols to workflow, XML and CORBA. For our purposes, we will stipulate that it is possible to convey data with its semantic interpretation (say, in XML) for a wide range of possible services. A client must be able to assemble, from different providers, a package of services that will enable it to achieve its mission.

For completeness, we mention briefly that cryptographic techniques support the transmission of protected information on public networks and media, the establishment of credentials to assemble a transaction or a group of services, as well as supporting decoupling of payment for services from the identity of the buyer. In particular, we stipulate that clients can obtain and use pseudonyms to interact with different services and servers.

Of special interest is the transmission of messages to clients without forcing the clients to give up their location and/or identity. This is achieved by the client listening

²The provider is the network server, which maintains the state of a mobile database in the original work on broadcast disks, and the mobile computers query it, possibly updating it via low-capacity uplinks.

for messages directed to it either by encryption using his/her public key (and obtained by decrypting using that key) or a message directed at a pseudonym (where pseudonyms are made available to trusted parties, e.g., colleagues). Completing certain transactions forces the client to transmit, i.e., to break its silence, for example, when a reservation or a bid may be part of obtaining a service. Furthermore, a client may need to express interest to secure a guarantee that the service (or other resource) will be available later, when needed. However, use of pseudonyms, cryptographically certified communications, etc. enable clients to still control part of its privacy.

3 An Example Scenario

We consider the scenario of a person spending a few hours at an airport, using her mobile computer to obtain information, communicate, obtain goods and services, all dependent on or enhanced by location-dependent information. Specifically, this person needs to query and receive information about flights status, receive off-airport notifications, assemble services to work, etc. In the remainder of this section, we develop this scenario to illustrate our approach.

Public Address System and Bulletin Board. As with conventional (audio) public-address systems and bulletin-board displays, a client may query for status and receive notifications of events of interest while silent. Examples include notification of flight delays, start of boarding, etc., deemed of general but local interest. These are location-aware information that can be broadcast throughout the airport. Interestingly, it is possible to give finer-grained notices as well: for example, an airline might broadcast the name or other unique identifier for a passenger (so that the corresponding client pays attention) as the header of an encrypted message notifying the passenger of a seat change or upgrade, or even a flight delay or gate change.

Although some of these services result in the client (or its principal) taking action, that action may or may not result in actual transmission. For example, a passenger obtaining an upgrade may still need to walk up to one of the airline's counters to get a new boarding pass. This action happens outside the mobile computing environment and thus preserves privacy with respect to servers. This is a common situation: a transaction encompasses electronic communication and physical actions whose disjoint nature provides a degree of privacy.

Delivery of Off-Airport Messages to Client. With cellular technology, a client receives communication traffic by registering itself with the network. However, a person might receive messages and (phone) calls originating off-airport if the sender of the message

knows that the person is likely to be at the airport. The sender might know this because of its association with the client (e.g., colleague) or because the client authorized the airline to release its location to authorized third parties. Specifically, the airline may know that the client is making a connection at this airport, that the incoming flight has landed and that the client has not yet boarded the outgoing flight. That is sufficient to localcast within the airport the call information (equivalent to "please pick up a white courtesy phone"). If it is a one-way message, the client may choose to not acknowledge it (as with audio PA systems) in order to remain silent. If the message or call requires the client to respond, it can still preserve some degree of privacy by responding through other channels.

Other Goods and Services. As with visual and audio advertising, retailers and service providers on the airport may offer goods and services local to (each part of) the airport. A client may include rules to find a place in which its principal will be served food, given access to office infrastructure and communication, by listening to localcast offers and composing them.

Business and Technology Implications. The entity owning the wireless communication facilities at the airport, the airline, and other parties can easily support the scenario described above by charging small amounts for delivering messages (or just broadcasting them). A client/principal traveling with a specific airline has already yielded significant privacy to that airline, which makes the airline the natural entity to relay off-airport communications to the localcast facility. The client/principal furthermore has a pre-existing relationship with the airline, for example, the airline may already have a public key for the customer/client/principal, as well as a means to verify credentials of outside parties wishing to communicate with the client while in its sphere of influence (i.e., from nearly the first checkin until the last deplane on a trip).

4 Conclusion

This paper is our first attempt to reconcile the conflicting goals of preserving a measure of privacy while benefiting from location-aware functionality by applying notions borrowed from the push-based model of mobile databases. We propose enhancing the privacy offered to mobile users of services that currently require clients to give away their location for most of their interactions. Instead of controlling access to the voluminous location information obtained by tracking mobile users, we propose minimizing the generation of such information in the first place.

Our approach is not applicable to applications that intrinsically need both 2-way communication and forms of authentication that prevent a client from withholding its

location or identity from the server. In that sense, our work complements existing work premised on clients always revealing that information; however, by proposing a shift from pull to push, we expect to make it easier to identify and support applications amenable to our approach. We have examined scenarios and possible applications, and indicated the promises of this approach.

References

- [1] S. Acharya, R. Alonso, M. Franklin, and S. Zdonik. Broadcast Disks: Data Management for Asymmetric Communications Environments. In *Proc. ACM SIGMOD Intl. Conf. on Management of Data*, pages 199–210, 1995.
- [2] M. Altinel and M. Franklin. Efficient Filtering of XML Documents for Selective Dissemination of Information. In *Proc. Intl. Conf. Very Large Databases. VLDB 2000*, pages 53–64, 2000.
- [3] A. Beresford and F. Stajano. Location Privacy in Pervasive Computing. *Pervasive Computing*, pages 46–55, Jan–Mar 2003.
- [4] S. Mazumdar and M. AbuSafiya. A Document-Centric Approach to Business Process Management. In *Proc. Intl. Conf. Information and Knowledge Engineering*, 2004. To Appear.
- [5] G. Myles, A. Friday, and N. Davies. Preserving Privacy in Environments with Location-Based Applications. *Pervasive Computing*, pages 56–64, Jan–Mar 2003.
- [6] C. Pedregal-Martin and K. Ramamritham. Guaranteeing Recoverability in Electronic Commerce. In *Proc. Intl. Wkshp. on Advanced issues of E-Commerce and Web-Based Information Systems*, pages 144–155, 2001.
- [7] C. Pedregal-Martin and K. Ramamritham. Support for Recovery in Mobile Systems. *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, 51(10):1219–1224, October 2002.
- [8] W. van der Aalst, M. Hofstede, and M. Weske. Business Process Management: A Survey. In *Proc. Intl. Conference on Business Process Management (BPM 2003)*, pages 1–12, 2003.